

CHESS SETUP: STEP 2

The pilots start to take shape on CHESS SETUP's first anniversary

Welcome to our 2nd newsletter, we wish you a pleasant reading

The European project investigating buildings' energy self-sufficiency

3rd meeting in Belfast

The partners held a meeting in Belfast last May, to review the work carried out during the past six months.

Hosted by the **Ulster University**, they also could visit its on-site heat pump and thermal storage installations, that could even constitute a 4th small-scale pilot!

The Pilots

Corby

In Corby, the 47 ecohomes' design has been defined to the smallest details. They will be characterized by their higher build quality, their ultra-low energy consumption, the use of solar hybrid photovoltaic and thermal panels and the Earth Energy Bank to store energy that will be used when required

Sant Cugat

In Sant Cugat, the pilot will finally supply the swimming pool's energy needs. A technical feasibility check has been carried out to evaluate the roof's reinforcement needs. On the other hand, the public tendering procedure is being launched install the solar hybrid panels, the thermal storage tank and the monitoring system.

Lavola's headquarters

In Manlleu, Chess Setup 2.0 came out: the solar hybrid panels will be replaced by photovoltaic ones (PV), and an air source heat pump (ASHP). The system has been optimized as the thermal energy produced by the hybrid panels would have mainly been lost due to the physical space limitations for the thermal storage tank and the lack of heating demand in summer in the existing office building. Thus, the thermal energy will be produced on demand by the ASHP when required to heat up the thermal storage. The electricity produced by the PV will be used to feed the ASHP and any excess during the year and especially in summer may be used to feed any other electric demands of the building.

Technical achievements

Those steps forward on site were made achievable thanks to the previous work carried on by all the partners.

- Wattia Innova designed **Chess Setup monitoring system**. It will include an external variable interface, to provide data about the weather forecasts and electricity prices, at the basis of the system's optimization.
- Barcelona Ecologia studied the **integration of other energy sources and technologies**, and the energy and CO2 savings it would induce.
- Veolia evaluated the different **heat storage tank's construction techniques**, and the regulatory framework that would have to be applied in the United-Kingdom and in Spain.
- The University of Ulster is directly working on the **heat pumps' design** in each of the pilots.

CSU in Copenhagen

Chess Setup will be introduced at the "3rd International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and 4th Generation District Heating" in Copenhagen on September 12th and 13th. Barcelona Ecologia will represent the consortium, and speak about the project's concept and execution. You know where to find us!

"I call on you to remain confident, we will succeed, because we are fully committed. Because wherever we live, whoever we are, we all share the same responsibility to **make our planet great again.**"
Emmanuel Macron, President of the French Republic

Self-consumption in Spain

The 2015-royal ban prohibiting collective self-consumption in Spain has been lifted on May 25th! The regional governments will be free to regulate this market on their own. This opens up the possibility to develop common self-consumption installations for housings, districts, or any buildings willing to mutualize the energy produced on site, to consume it, to store the eventual surplus, or to revert it into the energy supplier's grid. The decision generated enthusiasm among citizens, local authorities and the energy sector. Beyond the crucial lever it constitutes to the H2020 objectives' achievement, the National Federation of Electrical and Telecommunication installations' entrepreneurs (FENIE) had already **estimated the economic impact** it could have in Spain: more than 570 million euros between 2017 and 2020.

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